

Kinetics of Ag^+ Catalysed Oxidative Decarboxylation of Acetic Acid by Ce^{4+} in H_2SO_4 Medium

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The silver ion catalysed oxidative decarboxylation of acetic acid was studied to find the effect of Ag^+ on the mechanism of the reaction. The order of [acetic acid] and $[\text{Ag}^+]$ were found to be fractional and that of $[\text{Ce}^{4+}]$ as unity. The product analysis as carried out by *g.l.c.* indicates methanol and methyl acetate along with CO_2 . The rate law obtained is explained on the basis of adduct formation between Ag^+ and acetic acid, the adduct reacting in a slow step with Ce^{4+} to give the products. From the kinetic study, the formation constant (K) for the adduct and the bimolecular rate constant for the slow step were evaluated at various temperatures and from this the activation parameters have been calculated.

WILLARD and Young¹ have observed in their work on the oxidation of various organic acids that ceric sulphate was inactive towards formic and acetic acids. However, the oxidation of many of these acids was studied using ceric nitrate² and ceric perchlorate³ recently. Earlier work in this laboratory^{4,5} has shown that Ag^+ and Mn^{2+} act as good catalysts in the oxidations by ceric sulphate and hence it was thought worthwhile to employ Ag^+ catalyst in the case of reactions which do not proceed under uncatalysed conditions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of the reagent grade and the method of following the kinetics was the same as in our earlier paper⁶. The product analysis was carried out by gas-liquid partition chromatography using Aimil unit with a thermal conductivity detector. Methanol and methyl acetate were identified as the main products by the peak enhancement with authentic samples. CO_2 gas evolved was detected using baryta water. Evidence for the adduct formation of acetic acid with Ag^+ was obtained from the vibrational frequency of carboxylate anion of acetic acid. Carboxylic acids in general give rise to two bands, one at 1600 cm^{-1} and the other at 1370 cm^{-1} which are assigned to the symmetric and asymmetric $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibrations of the resonance stabilized carboxylate group. These bands are noticed in acetic acid at 1620 cm^{-1} and 1380 cm^{-1} respectively, and in the presence of Ag^+ these bands occur at 1625 cm^{-1} and 1370 cm^{-1} respectively. The lowering of the asymmetric band of the carboxylate ion is an indication of the interaction between the metal ion and the carboxylate anion. The intensity of the band was also found to increase with increase in Ag^+ ion concentration. Further the asymmetric band suffered larger shift to lower frequencies (1330 cm^{-1}) in the presence of a bivalent copper ion. The n.m.r. spectrum of acetic acid in the presence of

Ag^+ also provides a supporting evidence for the adduct formation. The OH signal of acetic acid appears at ($\tau = 1.93$) but in the presence of Ag^+ ions the OH signal moves up field ($\tau = 2.03$). On adduct formation between Ag^+ and carboxylate group the electron density around the hydrogen decreases, consequently the OH proton signal occurs at higher field.

Results and Discussions

Under the conditions $[\text{Ce}^{4+}] \ll [\text{acetic acid}]$ in the presence of Ag^+ the order of $[\text{Ce}^{4+}]$ was unity as seen from the plot of $\log \frac{a}{a-x}$ vs. time (Fig. 1A).

The order of [acetic acid] was found to be 0.55 (Fig. 1B) from the plot of $\log k'$ vs $\log [\text{acetic acid}]$. The rate of oxidation of acetic acid by Ce^{4+} increased with the increase in $[\text{Ag}^+]$. The order of $[\text{Ag}^+]$ was found to be 0.75 (Fig. 1C). The concentration of Ag^+ was found to be unchanged at the end of the reaction as indicated by the constant thiocyanate titre value. Induced polymerization of acrylamide was observed when it was added in the reaction mixture indicating the presence of free radicals. The reaction was studied in the temperature range $45^\circ\text{--}65^\circ$ to evaluate the activation parameters. Higginson *et al.*⁷ who studied the oxidation of Tl^+ and Hg_2^{2+} by Ce^{4+} observed that in the absence of a suitable substrate there is no reaction between Ce^{4+} and Ag^+ . This is understandable from the oxidation potentials of the $\text{Ag}^+/\text{Ag}^{2+}$ couple (-1.98 v) which is higher than $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{4+}$ couple (-1.45 v in H_2SO_4 and -1.61 in HNO_3). In the case of the cerous-ceric couple the oxidation potentials decrease in the order $\text{HClO}_4 > \text{HNO}_3 > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and this has been explained as due to heavy complexing with acid anions. In general it is now known that the oxidation potentials decrease with complexation of the free metal ion. Hence, it is likely that catalysis

by Ag^+ is possible if one expects complexation of Ag^+ ions with the substrate which could decrease the potential of $\text{Ag}^+/\text{Ag}^{2+}$ couple much below the value of $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{4+}$ couple, to facilitate oxidation by Ce^{4+} .

Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. (A) Plot of $\log \frac{a}{a-x}$ vs time

$[\text{Ce}^{4+}] = 0.0074M$; $[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}] = 1.0M$;
 $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.97M$; $\mu = 3.10M$; $[\text{Ag}^+] = 0.02M$;
 temp. = 65° .

(B) Plot of $\log k' + 3$ vs $\log [\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}] + 1$
 other conditions same as in (A) with varying HOAc.

(C) Plot of $\log k' + 3$ vs $\log [\text{Ag}^+] + 2$
 $[\text{Ce}^{4+}] = 0.0051M$; $[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}] = 3.20M$;
 $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$; temp. = 50° ; $\mu = 3.20M$.

(D) Plot of $\frac{1}{k'}$ vs $\frac{1}{[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}]}$
 conditions same as in (B).

The fractional order of [acetic acid] indicates that it may be involved in complex formation either with Ce^{4+} or Ag^+ . That no complex is formed in the reaction between Ce^{4+} and organic substrates in H_2SO_4 medium has been pointed out earlier⁶. Ag^+ is known to form colourless adducts with oxygen containing compounds with lone pair of electrons on oxygen atom⁸. In view of the evidence obtained for the adduct formation between Ag^+ and acetic acid from i.r. and n.m.r. studies, we assume the adduct formation as a first step before oxidation by Ce^{4+} . Similar conclusions were drawn from the n.m.r. spectra of isopropyl alcohol + Ag^+ system also⁹. If the adduct formation is taken the first step the reaction scheme could be represented as :

The formation of Ag^{2+} —substrate adduct was confirmed by adding bipyridyl to the reaction system which gave a brown coloured complex of Ag^{2+} with a characteristic absorption maximum at 454 nm (ref. 10). From the above mechanism the following rate equation could be derived :

$$\frac{d[\text{Ce}^{4+}]}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{Ce}^{4+}][\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}][\text{Ag}^+]}{1 + K[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}] + K[\text{Ag}^+]} \quad \dots \text{ I}$$

or

$$-\frac{2.303}{dt} \frac{d \log [\text{Ce}^{4+}]}{dt} = k' = \frac{kK[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}][\text{Ag}^+]}{1 + K[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}] + K[\text{Ag}^+]} \quad \dots \text{ II}$$

Where k' is the observed rate constant, k is the bimolecular rate constant (step ii), and K is the formation constant of the adduct (step i). Equation (I) accounts for the first order dependence of $[\text{Ce}^{4+}]$ and the fractional orders of $[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}]$ and $[\text{Ag}^+]$. Taking the reciprocals of equation (II) at constant $[\text{Ag}^+]$.

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}]} \left[\frac{1}{kK[\text{Ag}^+] + k} \right] + \frac{1}{k[\text{Ag}^+]} \quad \dots \text{ III}$$

from equation (III) it is clear that the plots of $\frac{1}{k'}$

vs $\frac{1}{[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}]}$ should be linear with an intercept.

Such a plot (Fig. 1D) was obtained in the present work. The k and K values were calculated from the intercept and slope of the above plots at different temperatures to evaluate the various thermodynamic parameters.

The table shows that the formation constant (K) of the adduct is low and that increase in temperature would further decrease its stability as indicated by ΔH value. The large negative value for the ΔS

could be explained due to the more compact structure of the adduct as compared to the Ag^+ and CH_3COOH reactants. The bimolecular rate constant has a

could be due to the less rigid structure of the activated complex.

TABLE—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS EVALUATED FROM K AND k DATA

Sl. No.	Parameter	Value
1	K l mol ⁻¹ at 55°	1.09
2	ΔH k.cal.mol ⁻¹	-15.35
3	ΔG k.cal.mol ⁻¹	-0.54
4	ΔS e.u.	-45.10
5	$k \times 10^3$ l mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ at 55°	5.60
6	ΔE^\ddagger k.cal.mole ⁻¹	17.76
7	ΔH^\ddagger k.cal.mol ⁻¹	17.10
8	ΔG^\ddagger k.cal.mol ⁻¹	22.60
9	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.	-16.74

fairly low value in spite of the catalyst being present. In the absence of catalyst under similar conditions there was no reaction. The ΔE^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger appear to be of the same magnitude as encountered in many solution reactions. The low ΔS^\ddagger value however

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